

RURITAGE

Heritage for Rural Regeneration

D7.3 Dialogue Breakfast

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2. Background Information

Table 1: technical Information

Project Full title	Rural regeneration through systemic heritage-led strategies	
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Dissemination level:	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (CO)	

Table 2: Revision History

CNH	Cultural & Natural Heritage
D	Deliverable
EDP	Entrepreneurial Discovery Process
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
WP	Work Package
M	Month
RHH	Rural Heritage Hub
RM	Role Model
R	Replicator
RIS3	Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialisation
SIA	Systemic Innovation Area

**CULTURAL AND
NATURAL HERITAGE
FOR REGIONAL SMART
SPECIALISATION
STRATEGIES**

**17th November
2020
09:30 - 12:00 (CET)**

**Breakfast at
Sustainability's**

EVENT REPORT

Full recording available [here](#)

3. General context

Deliverable D7.3 Dialogue Breakfast is the result of implementing Subtask 7.5.1 (with the same name). The initial subtask proposed a “dialogue with European policy-makers in Brussels” and was initially scheduled for M24 (May 2020). The restrictions imposed around Europe and Brussels, as a result of the COVID-19 health crisis made it impossible to have this event in person in the spring of 2020. Following the consultations with the project coordinator and the EU project officer, the deliverable was postponed to M31 (December 2020) and the format was changed to an online event.

The topic of the Dialogue Breakfast was defined in cooperation with the RURITAGE project consortium taking in account “the relevant issues at stake at that moment”. Considering that: (1) the process of defining the new Programming Period 2021-2027 was in its last phase, (2) in general local actors have a low awareness of Smart Specialisation concept and RIS3 processes and (3) many Regions are starting the process of updating their RIS3, it was concluded that, linking the topic of RIS3 and CNH was very useful both for the RURITAGE partners but also for other EU organisations.

Therefore, the Dialogue Breakfast aimed to bring in contact the experts and organisations working on RIS3 with the experts and organisations working on CNH, which until now are not naturally and strongly linked. In order to do this ICLEI Europe organised bilateral interviews with key experts and organisations from both professional spheres. These had helped to identify the key subtopics, challenges and opportunities. Finally, yet importantly, the knowledge received in implementing this subtask will be used as the starting point for organising the workshop with the representatives of the Board of Regions and the Policy Recommendations proposed under Task 6.5. Therefore we will be able to create synergy.

Below you can read about the knowledge exchanged and ideas shared by the speakers.

4. Overview

On Tuesday November 17th 2020, [ICLEI Europe](#) hosted the 35th Breakfast at Sustainability's online, focusing on Cultural & Natural Heritage for regional Smart Specialisation Strategies (RIS3). The event was organised in the context of [RURITAGE](#), a Horizon2020 project that turns rural areas into laboratories to demonstrate Cultural & Natural Heritage as an engine of regeneration.

The event brought together representatives of EU institutions, cultural experts, regional officers and rural stakeholders, to discuss the unexplored potential of combining Smart Specialisation with Cultural & Natural Heritage (CNH). As Europe's regions are revising their RIS3 for the new programming period (2021-2027), and as the European Commission is setting ambitious goals for a green recovery, it was a timely moment to revisit how investment in Research & Innovation for CNH can contribute to building a sustainable future for all.

The event was moderated by Stephania Xydia, Governance & Social Innovation Officer and Alexandru Matei, Senior Officer in Urban-Regional Innovation, under the guidance of Cristina Garzillo, Senior Coordinator on Culture & Cultural Heritage at ICLEI Europe. An esteemed panel of speakers surrounded the digital breakfast table:

- **Laurent de Mercey**
European Commission, Unit Smart and Sustainable Growth (DG REGIO)
- **Alessandro Rainoldi**
Head of Unit, Territorial Development, Joint Research Centre (European Commission)
- **Maciej Hofman**
Policy Officer, Culture - Cultural and creative sectors (DG EAC)

- **Prof. Luigi Fusco Girard**
Associate Professor at IRISS - Institute for Research on Innovation and Services for Development (Italy)
- **Gumersindo Bueno Benito**
General Director for Cultural Heritage, Region of Castilla y León (Spain)
- **Gabriela Macoveiu**
Director of the Communication, Innovation and External Cooperation Department at the North-East Regional Development Agency (Romania)
- **Prof. Simona Tondelli**
Full Professor of Urban and Regional Planning, University of Bologna
Project Coordinator of RURITAGE

The agenda and the flow of the discussion was designed based on the questions submitted during the registration process by over **250 participants** across Europe, expressing interest in the topic. According to the registration data, most participants had little or moderate familiarity with Research & Innovation Smart Specialisation Strategies. Apart from some Ruritage partners, the event attracted many cultural actors seeking to get informed and get involved in the process at regional level. It also attracted several regional representatives, currently working on RIS3 and looking to better advise their authorities or better integrate Heritage to their strategies. Finally, it engaged researchers working on regional development and heritage preservation, but also policy-makers looking for innovative examples and best practices.

5. Introduction

The morning was kicked-off by Stephania Xydia, who presented the agenda, the speakers and some technicalities for participants to make most of the online event. Then, **Prof. Simona Tondelli** gave an **introductory presentation of RURITAGE** and its innovative approach to rural regeneration. RURITAGE establishes a heritage-led paradigm based on the identification of 6 **Systemic Innovation Areas**: Pilgrimage, Local Food, Migration, Art & Festival, Resilience and Landscape.

The project features 20 **Role Models** with a successful track record of rural regeneration processes in different territories. In the context of the project, they have been engaged in 97 Role Model actions, providing 40 lessons learned. Six other rural areas have been engaged in the project as **Replicators**, discovering successful strategies through a multi-level and multidirectional knowledge exchange process. The RURITAGE paradigm is based on a **multi-stakeholder approach** which engages policy-makers, researchers, SME's, industries and citizens to co-design rural development strategies in Rural Heritage Hubs. The result is described in the six Replicators' **Regeneration Plans**, proposing ways to build upon the local tangible, intangible and digital heritage and implement concrete cross-cutting actions between the 6 Systemic Innovation Areas. The project is now engaging 18 additional Replicators in the process providing open tools and policy recommendations for local actors to develop their own regeneration plans. Key lessons learnt so far include:

- Engage key stakeholder with leadership and influence capacity
- Identify local leaders
- Ensure continuous communication to create long-lasting relationships
- Empower citizens establishing and supporting bottom-up initiatives
- Involve and engage public and private bodies to establish PPPs for the regeneration plan implementation and sustainability
- Involve and engage vulnerable groups
- Create and share a long-term vision

Moving on to the framing of the discussion, **Alexandru Matei** took the floor to introduce the topic of the 35th Breakfast@Sustainability's: **Cultural & Natural Heritage (CNH) for regional Smart Specialisation Strategies (RIS3)**. He identified a gap between RIS3 experts and CNH experts which ought to be bridged, and presented this event as an opportunity to strengthen understanding and synergies between the two sides. He stressed the timely moment of the event considering the [New Programming Period](#) that starts from January 2021 and the fact that most EU regions are currently in the process of updating their RIS3. In the first part, his presentation focused on key concepts and relevant vocabulary so as to create a common understanding for participants. He thus defined the concepts of **Smart Specialisation**, the **Entrepreneurial Discovery Process (EDP)** and the **Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialisation - RIS3**, the

interlinkages between the three concepts and the way they are contributing to the Cohesion Policy. In the second part, the role of the [S3 Platform](#) was highlighted, offering examples on how the [Eye@RIS3](#) tool and the newly established [Cultural and Creative Regional Ecosystems CCRE-S3](#) can be used. Last but not least, his intervention suggested an **integrated approach to heritage** encompassing cultural (tangible & intangible), digital and natural elements, and a broader understanding of innovation that can take different forms, including **social innovation**.

6. The state of play regarding RIS3 and the role of CNH

The first round of discussion, moderated by Alexandru Matei, aimed to provide a better understanding of the current developments on Research & Innovation Smart Specialisation Strategies and key insights on how local cultural assets can drive innovation-led development agendas.

Laurent de Mercey presented the state of the play regarding RIS3 for the new Programming Period and what has changed since the previous 2013-2020 Programming Period. He stressed that in the previous

Programming Period the RIS3 was introduced as an **ex-ante conditionality** and a powerful tool for member states and regions to receive ERDF funding and R&I investments, enabling stakeholders to define their priorities and concentrate their resources on specific topics. Thanks to smart specialisation, 40 billion euros of ERDF funding have been invested in R&I projects and 180 Regions have developed RIS3 with the support of the S3 Platform, managed by the JRC. RIS3 is a place-based approach, a bottom-up and dynamic process which enables Regions to identify strengths and strategic areas of intervention. Concerning the role of Heritage, Mr. de Mercey mentioned that 124 regions in 22 member states have already selected 185 RIS3 priorities that relate to the Cultural and Creative Industries. In the future programming period, RIS3 will become an **enabling condition for ERDF** and an emphasis will be given to **their good governance** in order for regions to receive ERDF funding under the Cohesion Policy Objective 1: A Smarter Europe, which is expected to absorb 80 out of the 200 billion euros of

the Cohesion Policy. Smart Specialisation Strategies are expected to play a greater role in the future, enhancing their scope beyond R&I in order to serve **four Specific Objectives** supported by the ERDF:

1. Enhancing R&I capacities and uptake of advanced technologies
2. Digitisation for citizens, companies and governments
3. Growth and competitiveness in SMEs
4. Developing skills for smart specialisation, industrial transition and entrepreneurship

All investments under these specific objectives should be consistent with a region's RIS3 and contribute to smart economic transformation. In the next Programming Period, RIS3 is also expected to have strong links with other programmes such as Horizon Europe, Digital Europe and the Single Market programme.

Alessandro Rainoldi reflected on whether regions need to update their RIS3 and what the role of CNH could be in this process. He noted that it's up to the regions to decide if they should modify their strategies compared to the previous Programming Period. Firstly, under the current **COVID-19 pandemic** situation, RIS3 can be a tool for shaping a **recovery process** that is based on the advantages and the strengths of each territory, as well as on the capacities and ambitions of local communities in both urban and rural landscapes. It is a tool that brings together knowledge from science, market, innovation, research in one territory but also the knowledge and values of the communities. Secondly, there is a need to consider the **global challenges** and the directionality of the European policy efforts towards **sustainability**, ensuring that each RIS3 contributes both to the achievement of the **SDGs** and to the **European Green Deal** objectives. In the new programming period such considerations need to be included up-front to the regional RIS3,

shaping a genuine transformation agenda for each territory. Rural areas have the opportunity to use Cultural and Natural Heritage to promote **innovation towards sustainability** and **build systems of innovation around local assets**. Current smart specialisation priorities in the culture and cultural heritage sector are not only just about tourism but also about technologies, built environment and immaterial priorities (e.g. 15 regions are prioritising culinary traditions and food systems). The next Programming Period gives us an opportunity to think outside the box!

Maciej Hofman argued on the potential of CNH to become a driver of innovation for Smart Specialisation Strategies. While reminding about Article 167 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) governing EU action in the cultural field, he stressed some of the strategic documents for the European Union on Culture:

- The [New European Agenda for Culture](#)
- The [European framework for action on cultural heritage](#)
- The [Work Plan for Culture 2019-2022](#)

These documents recognise the intrinsic value of Culture but also the role it can have for human wellbeing, economic growth etc. The new European Agenda for Culture refers to **cities and regions as natural partners for experimentation**, since they are on the forefront of local development, attract talent and remain very close to citizens' needs. Culture and Cultural Heritage is very well placed to give this **distinctive edge and the comparative advantage** required by RIS3 because of its **diversity** across the EU, as long as we use strategic thinking, across silos and policies. The **European Capitals of Culture** is a good example on how thinking of Culture as a strategic resource can contribute to local regional development: the preparation starts 6 years ahead of the title, developing detailed plans for territorial transformation, and leaving a legacy for the future.

Prof. Luigi Fusco Girard commented on how Smart Specialisation of Heritage can be integrated with Cultural Strategies. He stressed that Smart Specialisation of the rural heritage in particular should be interpreted through the perspective of the **circular economy model**: Smart means Circular, offering a **culture of collaboration, synergies and integration**. He highlighted the existing disequilibrium between the city and the countryside and how the COVID-19 pandemic has shifted the attention from the centre to the periphery, thanks to ICT technologies. In these marginal areas cultural and natural heritage is often an unused or underused resource. The **smart innovative strategy** is the re-use of these assets as **living systems** in a circular economy model for the territory, stimulating not only innovations in technologies but also in terms of values/culture for a human-centred

development.

Firstly, it is necessary to define an ecosystem for CNH circular reuse in the rural, marginal and inner areas through the lens of **bio-ecology** and **agro-ecology**: build a self-sustainable/auto-poietic¹ system, identifying and organizing systemic complementarities with integration of many different functions/activities (e.g. the production of food, energy, water, fertilizers, livestock, nutrients). Presenting the **Tripod Model** (see the graphic in the video) developed within the [CLIC project](#). Prof. Fusco Girard spoke about the regenerative, the generative and the symbiotic capacity of such systems. He stressed that **building research capacity and innovative technological tools** is essential for closing the loops in the adaptive circular reuse of CNH. Furthermore, the circular economy is not only limited to specific economic, environmental, social impacts, but offers a new cultural horizon. The circular economy is grounded on the **culture of cooperation**, and thus on **reciprocal trust**. We need today to regenerate not only the heritage assets but also the current

culture in a more solidaristic perspective. We need to reshape the New Green Deal strategy into a cultural, human strategy.

Gumersindo Bueno Benito presented how the region of Castilla y León in Spain has integrated Cultural & Natural Heritage to its RIS3. He argued that CNH enhanced by the **Spanish language** (Castellano) and combined with tourism, could become a driver for smart specialisation and economic growth. Overall, the Region has identified four thematic priorities in its RIS3:

- Agriculture
- Manufacturing (notably car manufacturing)
- Health Social care and demographic challenge
- Cultural Heritage and Spanish Language

After a process of analysis, it became clear that CNH as an endogenous resource could be a fourth thematic priority for the RIS3, enhancing **competitiveness, innovation and internationalisation**. The key challenge was to combine these assets with scientific and technological specialisation. The projected impacts are to increase the number of research and innovation projects, enable the **progressive use of technologies in all aspects of cultural heritage management**, and improve the **professional skills** and international cooperation of public and private actors in the cultural sector.

> [Watch a short video about the Cultural & Natural Heritage of Castilla y León: *Vive Castilla y León ¡Castilla y León es Vida!*](#)

¹ The term autopoiesis (from Greek *αὐτο-* (*auto-*) 'self', and *ποίησις* (*poiesis*) 'creation, production') refers to a **system** capable of reproducing and maintaining itself.

Gabriela Macoveiu shared the experience of the North-East Romania region, which did not include cultural heritage in the first edition of the RIS3, but is now prioritising CNH for the next Programming Period. She referred to the growing maturity of the ecosystem of local stakeholders who are able to focus on a vision for the sector and develop a strategy based on the competitive advantages of the region. The new RIS3 prioritises **tourism** acknowledging the potential of CNH and the expertise of 7 Universities in the region. The challenge now is to bring innovation between multiple stakeholders who work on agro-tourism, marketing, research etc and to relate CNH to other sectors, such as information technology, bio-technology and agri-food. Nowadays there is a stronger ecosystem of stakeholders: there is a new cluster created with a strong vision for the attractiveness and promotion of the region, including innovative solutions; there are also two **certified eco-tourism destinations** (the [buffalo land](#) and Bucovina land) which combine CNH with responsible research projects. Currently there are 3 niches of specialisation for tourism: **tourism for healthy living** (e.g. climatotherapy), **eco-tourism** (e.g. circular farms), and **cultural tourism**. In the next Programming Period, the need is to support innovative projects valorising cultural and natural heritage using two additional instruments: the [Local Action Groups \(LAG\)](#) especially in rural areas and Integrated Urban Development instrument.

> [Watch a short video about the Cultural & Natural Heritage of North-East Romania Romania - North-East Region - Enriches your soul!](#)

Following this first round of inputs, **Prof. Simona Tondelli** shared her reflections on the similarities between the **Entrepreneurial Discovery Process (EDP)** required to build a RIS3 and the **regeneration process developed** within RURITAGE, both **being place-based** and **bottom-up**. Through this multi-stakeholder engagement, local strategies gain in terms of **feasibility**, fostering commitment and a sense of **ownership**. She stressed the need to scale up local co-creation processes so as to influence regional policies and better position CNH within RIS3. **Combining academic knowledge and the local knowledge of the community**, connecting Universities, enterprises, local administrations and citizens is key in the effort to link local action to global goals. Lastly, she highlighted the importance of a **human-centred** approach, **adaptability** and **resilience** so as to adapt to constant change while remaining true to local values.

> [Read the RURITAGE Vision Paper on “Thinking beyond COVID-19”](#)

7. Reflections on lessons learnt and future directions

The second round of discussion, moderated by Stephania Xydia, focused on how we can improve the placement of CNH in RIS3 developed for the next programming period.

Laurent de Mercey was invited to comment on why CNH remains marginal in RIS3 processes. He gave an optimistic perspective, stressing that the cultural sector is in a strategic position to promote **smart, sustainable and inclusive growth** in all EU regions and cities, making an essential contribution to the EU's overall growth strategy. Investments in the area of culture can have a positive impact on the economy, address social challenges and create jobs, provided that investments are carried out under an economic rationale. In that respect there is indeed an advance of some regions compared to others. **Mapping regional assets**, relevant **stakeholders** and their respective **potential** using a **quadruple helix approach** is fundamental to the RIS3 development process and it is the regional and national authorities who are responsible in ensuring bottom-up involvement. Furthermore, it is important for actors to create linkages between ERDF funding and other EU programmes such as **Creative Europe, Cosme** and **Horizon Europe**.

Alessandro Rainoldi explained how the **Entrepreneurial Discovery Process** facilitates **multi-level governance**. It is about pulling resources, capacities and knowledge together, empowering stakeholders at different territorial levels in order to combine the vision of a regional authority for the future, with what the community thinks. There are a variety of mechanisms that can be used - one of the challenges is to understand that everyone can have a say. Multilevel governance is a **learning-by-doing process**. Local communities, urban and rural, should engage in the smart specialisation debate in their own territory and do their part in influencing policies at the regional level. JRC has worked with the [Region of Extremadura \(Spain\)](#) to build a RIS3 around a PDO² food, “La Torta del Casar” a type of cheese, which has grown into a real smart specialisation asset, leading to investments such as a Shepherding School, involving farmers,

² Protected Designation of Origin

shepherds, tourism experts, cultural organisations and other local actors. Experience shows that the debate starting from the local level can support building a specific case at the regional but also national level. Multi-level governance also has an international, **trans-regional dimension**, as Regions join [thematic platforms](#) to collaborate on similar priority areas (e.g. [Cultural & Creative Regional Ecosystem Partnership](#)) and build consortia to absorb funding from different sources (e.g. INTERREG, Horizon Europe).

Maciej Hofman commented on the promising innovation trends in CNH and presented some relevant examples funded by the Creative Europe Programme. "[Culture for Cities and Regions](#)" is a peer-learning project for local authorities, led by EURO CITIES and ERRIN which has developed [70 Case studies](#) (2015-2017) through 15 [study visits](#) and 10 peer learning sessions (e.g. the case of Aquileia, in Italy which has prioritised Culture & Tourism in its Smart Specialisation Strategy, involving the local population in the preservation of the archaeological park). A key challenge is to **break silos between departments within regional authorities** so as to connect Culture with other sectors (e.g. Education). Cities like Helsinki and Saint Étienne demonstrate the benefits of **engaging designers as facilitators** of multi-level governance and cross-departmental collaboration. The need for **openness and flexibility** was also mentioned in relation to the [European Capitals of Culture](#), showcasing examples like Aarhus and Galway that go beyond the urban limits to create impact in peri-urban and rural areas. Relevant resources in this field include the "[Cultural Heritage in Action](#)" (see the [catalogue of 32 of best practices](#)), and the "[Voices for Culture](#)" report on "[The role of culture in non-urban areas of the EU](#)" which also features Ruritage.

Prof. Fusco Girard was invited to present some examples of research and innovation projects valorising CNH, from his experience in Italy. In particular, he referred to the **Sanità District in the periphery of Naples** which was characterised by growing inequalities and social issues. By investing in human capital and a new

vision for the future, existing cultural resources were used to bring about real change for the local community. Initially, the archaeological area became the economic engine to attract visitors and sustain additional educational, social, sanitary functions. Young generations were actively involved in the strategic **adaptive reuse of unused churches, archeological sites and catacombs** stimulating the sense of co-belonging and community. **New functions** included a business incubator, a recording studio, a theatre, a school and other vital spaces for personal and community growth. The **strategic adaptive reuse of public spaces based on real local needs**, led to stronger community bonds, a sense of local pride and confidence that "together we can change", which is fundamental to local development.

Gumersindo Bueno Benito commented on the key lessons learnt from the experience of Castilla y León. He stressed that **CNH is not a product** for tourism, but supports the **wellbeing** of people. It is

important to enhance cultural assets combining interrelations and **clustering stakeholders** (universities, companies etc) at the regional, national and international level. All the initiatives cannot solely be in the hands of the regional administration, but the regional administration can support bottom-up initiatives. In the context of RIS3 we need to have in mind that **technology is an instrument but not the goal**. His recommendation to other regions (and to himself!) would be to maintain a good budget, reduce bureaucracy and **simplify procedures** and foster **entrepreneurship** which is crucial for the future of rural and urban areas. We should not forget the **importance of intangible heritage** and always try to strengthen the voice of **grassroots**, civic organisations. The Green Deal, the **demographic challenge** and global

competitiveness are some of the key areas in which the CNH sector can have substantial contributions, as long as it “stays connected to real life”.

Gabriela Macoveiu was invited to share advice to cultural actors interested in engaging in RIS3 processes. She motivated them to **get actively engaged**, get in touch with their regional representatives and participate in EDP workshops or project development labs in their territory. She stressed that such processes require a **continuity** and sophisticated methodologies in order to create the right synapses that generate innovative ideas. We need to keep in mind that **RIS3 cannot cover all the gaps** left by other development strategies so we should be careful in terms of setting expectations and avoiding frustrations during implementation. It’s important to share information, identify local leaders / frontrunners and **understand the EDP terminology** in order to avoid stakeholders getting lost in translation. The core question is “What makes your idea an innovative idea?” and how can it lead to innovative services, products or processes? Identifying the right platform for implementation, using **diverse funding sources** and being open to modify/adapt a project to the realities of the territory is key for the local ecosystem to flourish.

> More information on local projects in North-East Romania can be found at the following link: https://www.adrnordest.ro/index.php?page=DISCOVER_TOURISM

Following the second round of inputs, the moderators stressed that the Entrepreneurial Discovery Process is a two-way process: Some regions are more active in inviting and engaging stakeholders, others require some bottom-up pressure in order to open up the dialogue about RIS3, so it is worth to **identify your local in the Eye@RIS3 platform** and knock on their door!

In the **final round of reflections**, the following question was selected from the chat and openly asked to

the panel:

“Very often, academia uses a language and **vocabulary** which feels deliberately lofty and off-putting. I feel that this is a general problem between information silos. How can we overcome this basic problem?”

Alessandro Rainoldi mentioned a simple example of being lost in translation around the word “Region” which in the EU context has a completely different meaning than in the UN context (in which the EU is a world region). To overcome misunderstandings we need to open up new channels of communication across sectors and disciplines. A good example is the case of [Lapland in Finland](#), which faced challenges in terms of geographical and population distribution but managed to develop a toolbox for communities to

talk to each other and come up with a very successful RIS3 which integrates CNH. **Gabriela Macoveiu** emphasised the importance of **building trust** between stakeholders before launching RIS3 initiatives. This can happen through preparatory meetings and online portals in which stakeholders present themselves and share news, building a **platform of dialogue** that develops as an **ecosystem of stakeholders**. **Maciej Hofman** acknowledged the vocabulary challenge as a broader issue within EU institutions and how they communicate with different audiences. He stressed the **role of the offices of regions in Brussels** as interfaces between EU policy and local action, and their responsibility to translate the diverse opportunities for citizens in their regions. He invited participants to join the [Public Consultation on the Future of rural areas](#) launched by the European Commission which serves as a useful interface for broader dialogue and can benefit from grassroots input from rural networks.

8. Concluding remarks

At the closure of the event, **Prof. Simona Tondelli** took the lead in summarising the main points of the discussion, also addressing some of the questions from the chat. First, she focused on the concept of **social innovation** that also addresses the issues of the different ethnical composition of many rural areas, explaining how through a participatory approach and empowering citizens, the challenge of **migration** can turn into a driver for rural regeneration (i.e. as in RURITAGE’s Role Model *Piam Onius Asti*). Another challenge for rural areas addressed in the chat is the difficulty to address the built heritage in rural areas, due mainly to lack of funds. She highlighted how this challenge can be overturned, thanks to the presence of a rich and scattered **built heritage** that can easily be reused, also thanks to the low renting or buying prices (compared to urban areas).

The example of the Naples’ San Gennaro [Catacombs](#) presented by Prof. Fusco Girard demonstrated a key factor in heritage regeneration: **mixed uses**. She then explained that building systems of innovation around CNH in rural areas requires **networking and clustering** around competitive assets, in an inclusive process that provides continuity. Local administrations should act as enablers of this bottom-up approach, fostering **multilevel governance**, adapting to the specific conditions, constantly “**learning-by-doing**”. As demonstrated by RURITAGE processes for rural regeneration, the **analysis of good practices** can lead to tailoring solutions to fit local challenges and objectives. Finally, she stressed the need for a

holistic approach in EU, national, regional and local policies, building up **synergies among different funding sources** (ERDF, H2020, Creative Europe, CAP, etc) for enhancing the rich CNH of EU rural areas.

9. Next Steps

Alexandru Matei commented that the 35th Breakfast at Sustainability's was part of a broader research conducted by ICLEI Europe in the framework of the RURITAGE project, which will conclude in the development and publication of **Policy Recommendations** on the integration of Cultural & Natural Heritage to regional Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialisation. In this framework, an **open call for regions will be launched** to establish the **RURITAGE Board of Regions**. **These regional representatives will be involved in a** policy workshop, which will be hosted by ICLEI Europe in autumn 2021. Therefore ICLEI invited the participants to **express their interest** to become one of the members of the Board of Regions. Together we are stronger!

10. Additional Resources

- [Eye on RIS3 Platform](#)
- [RIS3 of the Region Castilla y León \(Spain\)](#)
- [RIS3 of the North-East Region \(Romania\)](#)
- Report [“Linking Culture to Smart Specialisation Strategies”](#) (2020) developed by TASO DESARROLLOS S.L. in the framework of the ROCK project
- Paper [“Circular Economy Concepts for Cultural Heritage Adaptive Reuse Implemented Through Smart Specialisations Strategies”](#) developed by Uppsala University in the framework of the CLIC project
- Report [Circular governance models for adaptive reuse of cultural heritage](#) developed by ICLEI Europe in the framework of the CLIC project

11. Acknowledgments

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